

A Hybrid AI Framework for Explainable Hate Speech Analysis and Context-Aware Misinformation Verification in Sinhala under Sri Lanka’s Online Safety Act

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Abstract. Addressing the need for transparent and legally accountable Sinhala language content moderation, this paper presents a novel hybrid AI framework aligned with Sri Lanka’s Online Safety Act. The framework integrates two key components: (i) an explainable hate speech detection system based on a fine-tuned XLM-RoBERTa-base transformer model, achieving 92.55% accuracy and 0.9222 F1-score, with interpretability provided through LIME, SHAP, and contrastive explanations; and (ii) a multi-agent misinformation verification system combining domain classification, Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG), and real-time web search. RAGAS evaluation demonstrates strong faithfulness (0.74–0.80) and factual correctness (0.70–0.79), validating both reliability and context awareness. This research represents the first Sinhala-focused AI moderation system aligned with national legal mandates. It advances low-resource NLP, demonstrates the feasibility of legally compliant automated moderation, and offers a scalable model for high-stakes content verification, with architectural principles adaptable to AI-assisted decision making in critical domains such as judicial decision support, healthcare, and national security.

Keywords: multi-agent AI, explainable AI, Sinhala language, hate speech analysis, misinformation verification, Online Safety Act

1 INTRODUCTION

Online hate speech and misinformation pose significant challenges in the digital era, undermining public discourse and eroding trust in reliable information, with tangible real-world consequences. In Sri Lanka, a nation shaped by ethnic and religious diversity and a history of conflict, these digital threats intensify existing social tensions. Events such as the 2019 Easter Sunday attacks and the COVID-19 pandemic revealed how social media can amplify hate speech and misinformation, leading to communal violence and undermining public health efforts.

There were occasions when the government took drastic measures, temporarily blocking social media to slow the rapid spread of harmful content. Yet, these measures barely scratched the surface, leaving the root causes unchecked. Despite the diligent work of fact-checking organizations such as Fact Check, AFP Fact Check Sri Lanka, Fact Crescendo, and Hashtag Generation, manual efforts are frequently overwhelmed by the massive volume and velocity of online content. By the time a fact-checked report is published, misinformation amplified by social media algorithms has often already gone viral, causing significant harm. Furthermore, these crucial fact-checked reports often go unnoticed by the wider public, remaining disconnected from everyday online conversations where misinformation spreads.

Acknowledging these growing digital threats, the Sri Lankan government enacted the Online Safety Act, No. 9 of 2024. This legislation establishes a legal framework to combat hate speech and misinformation, providing a crucial mandate for addressing online harm. However, the Act has sparked debate. Concerns have been raised regarding the balance between online safety and freedom of expression. Critics argue that the Act’s broad definitions and vague language can be misused for political censorship. Therefore, solutions aimed at operationalizing the Online Safety Act must prioritize transparency and accountability.

Despite its legislative intent and the framework it establishes, the Act alone is not a complete solution. Like manual fact-checking efforts, enforcing the Act against the constant stream of millions of social media posts requires an approach beyond human capacity. Existing automated methods, primarily developed for high-resource languages, often fail to capture the nuanced linguistic, morphological, and semantic intricacies of Sinhala.

Given these limitations, there is a clear need for a hybrid artificial intelligence framework that not only detects hate speech and misinformation accurately but also provides explainable outputs and context-aware verification. Such a framework is essential for the effective implementation of the Online Safety Act and for ensuring that measures to safeguard online safety do not compromise fundamental democratic rights.

In response to these challenges, a hybrid AI framework has been developed that integrates explainable hate speech analysis with multi-agent misinformation verification, specifically tailored for the Sinhala language and aligned with Sri Lanka’s legal context. This study explores the design, development, and evaluation of this framework, with particular emphasis on transparency and scalability.

2 RELATED WORK

2.1 Legal and Regulatory Foundations

The foundation of this research is anchored in the Online Safety Act, No. 9 of 2024 [1], which serves as a comprehensive legislative framework aimed at ensuring safety in online communications within Sri Lanka. Research in fairness, accountability, and transparency (FAccT) has increasingly emphasized that algorithmic decision-making must be both socially contextualized and auditable.

The concept of algorithmic fairness has evolved to address power dynamics, with situated approaches gaining traction for sociotechnical systems [2]. Despite these advancements, none of the aforementioned FAccT frameworks have yet been adapted to Sinhala NLP systems. This absence presents a critical gap in ensuring that AI-driven content moderation aligns with both local legal mandates and socio-cultural expectations.

Early efforts in Sinhala hate-speech detection treated the problem as a straightforward binary classification task on limited, manually labelled datasets [3]. A significant milestone in this area was the release of the Sinhala Offensive Language Dataset (SOLD), which contains 10,000 tweets annotated for offensive content [4]. Experiments involving multilingual transformer models, such as mT5, revealed that Sinhala lags high-resource languages by approximately 10 F1 points [5]. Further evaluations demonstrated that XLM-RoBERTa-base achieved a macro-F1 score of 83.49%, surpassing more conventional architectures such as LSTM, which reached 75.30% [6]. More recently, a new 4,168-sample Twitter–YouTube dataset enabled fine-tuning XLM-RoBERTa-base with a bidirectional RNN layer, yielding 88.3% and 91.2% F1 on the Twitter–YouTube and Kaggle corpora, respectively [7].

Although recent Sinhala hate speech detectors achieve high accuracy, their opaque “black-box” nature undermines legal accountability under Sri Lanka’s Online Safety Act [1]. Explainable AI (XAI) remedies this by revealing model rationales: Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations (LIME) perturbs inputs and fits a simple model locally to highlight influential tokens [8], and has been applied to multilingual and code-switched hate speech contexts [9]. SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) assigns feature contributions based on Shapley values, ensuring both local fidelity and global consistency in deep learning pipelines [10, 11]. Contrastive explanations further improve interpretability by attributing differences between target and foil classes [12]. However, despite these promising developments, such explainability frameworks have not yet been widely adapted to Sinhala NLP systems. This represents a critical gap, as the lack of interpretability in Sinhala-language hate speech models limits their legal accountability and restricts stakeholder confidence in automated moderation systems [13].

Misinformation detection in Sinhala has progressed from static classifiers to hybrid, context-aware pipelines—such as autoencoder-based anomaly detection capturing deviations in text, social graphs, and multimedia [14]—yet evaluations on unseen but related datasets report up to 50% accuracy drops due to domain shift [15], and LLM-based detectors, without continual updates or external retrieval, fail to catch emerging falsehoods in dynamic environments [16], underscoring the urgent need for real-time, context-aware systems.

Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) enhances misinformation detection by grounding generative models in retrieved evidence—first proposed to mitigate knowledge cutoffs in closed LLMs by fetching relevant documents before response generation [17] and further improved through domain classification to target specialized knowledge areas [18], while multi-agent extensions dynami-

cally coordinate specialized agents to iteratively refine verification plans under oversight, addressing the complexity of modern misinformation landscapes [19].

3 METHODOLOGY

This research employed a Design Science Research (DSR) paradigm, focusing on the design, development, and evaluation of a novel hybrid AI framework for Sinhala online content moderation, in alignment with Sri Lanka’s Online Safety Act. A mixed-methods research design was adopted, combining constructive, quantitative, and qualitative approaches. The framework comprises two main modules: a multi-agent context-aware misinformation verification system and an explainable hate speech analysis system. The high-level architecture is depicted in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. High-level architecture of the hybrid AI framework

3.1 Multi-Agent Context-Aware Misinformation Verification System

This system was designed to dynamically verify the veracity of Sinhala claims by integrating Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) with real-time web search, overcoming limitations of static knowledge bases and LLM knowledge cutoffs. The approach leverages a multi-agent architecture, implemented using the LangChain framework, for modularity and specialized task handling, including domain narrowing. Extensive Sinhala prompt engineering was crucial for enabling agents to process and generate contextually relevant Sinhala responses. The system orchestrates several specialized agents, as illustrated in Figure 2.

The Orchestration Agent oversees and coordinates the entire misinformation verification workflow. The Domain Classification Agent categorizes input statements into domains—politics, economics, or health—to guide targeted retrieval

Fig. 2. Multi-agent misinformation verification system workflow.

from domain-specific vector stores. The Data Retrieval Agent extracts semantically relevant information using similarity search within the assigned domain. The Decision Agent determines whether internally retrieved information is sufficient or if an external web search is needed. The Fact Analysis Agent synthesizes evidence from retrieved and/or web-based sources to generate reasoned analyses in Sinhala, applying output formatting as needed. Finally, the Verdict Agent refines the analysis into a standardized and concise final output. Except for the Decision Agent, which uses gemini-2.0-flash-thinking-exp-01-21, all other agents utilize gemma-3-27b-it.

The system utilized two data modalities: an internal knowledge base and external real-time data. The internal knowledge base consists of domain-specific factual information on Sri Lanka, organized into curated datasets and stored in vector databases to enable efficient semantic search. Text was preprocessed into overlapping chunks and embedded for retrieval based on content relevance within each domain. The external real-time data component complements this by using live web search to access current information, with results filtered for relevance to Sri Lanka and optionally limited to trusted news sources. Internally, the system uses ChromaDB for vector storage, Tavily Search API for live search, and relies on multilingual sentence transformers for embedding text.

The system was implemented in Python, utilizing Google’s Gemini API, LangChain, ChromaDB, Sentence Transformers, Tavily API, and Streamlit for the interactive user interface.

Quantitative assessment of the RAG component was performed using the RAGAs (Retrieval-Augmented Generation Assessment) framework. A dataset of 150 manually crafted domain-specific Sinhala claims (50 per domain: politics, economics, health) with ground truth references was created. Faithfulness, Context Recall, and Factual Correctness (F1) metrics were computed to assess the RAG component’s ability to retrieve relevant information and generate accurate responses.

3.2 Explainable Hate Speech Detection System

This component focused on accurately identifying hate speech in Sinhala text while providing transparent classification decisions through Explainable AI (XAI) techniques. The system workflow is shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Explainable hate speech analysis system workflow

Five publicly available Sinhala hate speech datasets (including SOLD and various Facebook/Twitter corpora) were merged into a unified corpus, with labels standardized to a binary format and the data split into stratified training (80%), validation (10%), and test (10%) sets, while the validation and test sets were intentionally left unaltered to reflect real-world distributions. The training portion was deduplicated to prevent overfitting, and selective augmentation (character deletion and word swapping) was applied to the minority class. Text inputs were tokenized using the XLM-RoBERTa tokenizer (max length 128), and a pre-trained XLM-RoBERTa-base model (dropout 0.3) was fine-tuned via AdamW ($lr = 2e-5$) over five epochs with early stopping, batch size 16, and 5-fold stratified cross-validation on a Tesla T4 GPU.

Three XAI techniques were implemented to provide transparency into classification decisions. The framework incorporates multiple explanation techniques to enhance transparency in Sinhala hate speech detection. LIME generates local, interpretable explanations by perturbing input text and identifying influential tokens, using a tokenizer tailored for Sinhala script. SHAP attributes the impact of each token on the model’s predictions based on principles from cooperative game theory, offering clear visual insights aligned with Sinhala language structures. Contrastive Explanations emphasize the features that distinguish a predicted class from alternative classes by analyzing input gradients and identifying the most influential tokens. These techniques were implemented using LIME, SHAP, and Captum libraries, each customized for compatibility with Sinhala text and tokenization. These methods collectively enhance transparency, auditability, and potential contestability of model decisions, crucial for regulatory oversight.

Key limitations include the constrained availability of large, high-quality Sinhala misinformation datasets, leading to a qualitative evaluation for the full fact verification system and a RAGAs evaluation only for the RAG component. The current study does not cover linguistic variations like Romanized Sinhala or code-mixing. While XAI provides insights, their full legal admissibility and fidelity to complex LLM behavior require further investigation. Dependence on external APIs (Google Gemini, Tavily) and GPU resources presents operational and scalability challenges. The lack of direct baselines for the integrated hybrid framework made direct comparative evaluation challenging.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Presentation of Results

Multi-Agent Fact Verification System Results Qualitative evaluation demonstrated the system’s ability to process Sinhala claims, dynamically retrieve information (from internal vector stores or real-time web search), generate verification analyses, and provide standardized verdicts. Quantitative evaluation of the RAG component using RAGAs is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. RAGAs evaluation metrics for the Fact Verification System’s RAG component

Metric	Politics	Economics	Health
Faithfulness	0.8013	0.7708	0.7424
Context Recall	0.6859	0.8083	0.7636
Factual Correctness (F1)	0.7002	0.7996	0.7530

Explainable Hate Speech Detection System Results Performance of the fine-tuned `FacebookAI/xlm-roberta-base` model on the held-out test set is presented in Table 2. Qualitative results from error analysis and XAI evaluation are detailed in Section 4.2.

Table 2. Performance Metrics for Sinhala Hate Speech Detection Model

Metric	Value
Accuracy	0.9255
Precision	0.9098
Recall	0.9350
F1-score	0.9222

4.2 Analysis

Example 1 (Sufficient internal data): For a claim in Sinhala, translated as: "Applying coconut oil below the knee can prevent dengue infection". The system followed the RAG path. The domain classification agent correctly identified the domain as health. The data retrieval agent successfully retrieved relevant information from the health vector store contradicting the claim. The decision agent determined internal data was sufficient. The fact analysis agent then synthesized the data, producing an analysis and preliminary verdict in Sinhala (refer to Figure 4). The claim was determined false based on the absence of scientific evidence in the internal knowledge base. The Verdict Agent extracted the standardized verdict: "false".

Fig. 4. System output demonstrating verification using sufficient internal data.

Example 2 (Insufficient internal data, Triggering search): For a Sinhala claim, translated as: "Pro Care (Pvt) Ltd., Shade of Procure (Pvt) Ltd have been approved in Sri Lanka". The system triggered a real-time web search, as the claim required recent official information not in a static knowledge base. The domain classification agent identified the domain as economics. The decision

agent determined internal data was insufficient, initiating a real-time search via the Tavily API. Based on search results indicating prohibited pyramid schemes, the fact analysis agent produced an analysis and preliminary verdict in Sinhala (refer to Figure 5). The verdict agent extracted the standardized verdict: "false".

Fig. 5. System output demonstrating verification using real-time web search.

These examples indicated the system effectively leveraged both internal knowledge (via RAG) and real-time external information (via web search). Modular agent architecture facilitated clear task separation, and Sinhala prompt engineering enabled coherent Sinhala responses. Dynamic switching between RAG and search contributed to context-awareness.

Analysis of Fact Verification System Quantitative Results (RAGAs)

The RAGAs evaluation provided quantitative metrics for the RAG component’s output quality based on retrieved context and generated responses, relative to ground truth. Results for the RAG-only component are in Table 1. Faithfulness scores (0.7424 to 0.8013) indicate significant support for generated content from retrieved documents, suggesting effective grounding and minimal hallucination. Context Recall scores (0.6859 to 0.8083) measure relevant information capture, indicating some gaps in static knowledge base retrieval for comprehensive answers. Factual Correctness (F1) scores (0.7002 to 0.7996) show reasonable accuracy, but scores below 1.0 highlight instances of imperfect synthesis or incomplete retrieval.

The RAGAs evaluation underscores limitations of solely relying on a static knowledge base, providing quantitative justification for including real-time web search and the automatic hybrid workflow. The multi-agent system’s dynamic switching mechanism to external search when internal RAG is insufficient is

crucial for overcoming static knowledge limitations. This hybrid approach ensures access to current and comprehensive online information, improving context-awareness and verification accuracy for dynamic claims.

Analysis of Hate Speech Detection Quantitative Results Quantitative results (Table 4.2) indicate strong performance by the fine-tuned XLM-ROBERTa model on Sinhala hate speech detection. High Accuracy (0.9255) and F1-score (0.9222) demonstrate effective distinction between hate and non-hate speech, balancing precision and recall for content moderation. The model’s effectiveness is attributed to rigorous data preparation, including combining multiple Sinhala hate speech datasets (total 33,537 instances) for increased volume and diversity. Deduplication of the training set (from 26,829 to 17,667 instances) prevented overfitting, while maintaining duplicates in evaluation sets ensured realistic assessment. Data augmentation on the minority hate speech class (initial training 10,032 non-hate vs. 7,635 hate) addressed class imbalance, significantly contributing to high Recall and F1-score.

Fig. 6. Misclassified Sinhala statements by Facebook moderation system.

Analysis of Explainability Features (XAI) Integrated XAI techniques were qualitatively evaluated using real-world Sinhala examples (Figure 6) to demonstrate their effectiveness in providing interpretable explanations where existing moderation systems fail. Notably, the fine-tuned model was able to correctly classify such challenging cases.

LIME (Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations): When applying LIME to sample Sinhala texts, it effectively highlighted specific words or phrases locally contributing to the prediction(as indicated in Figure 7).

Fig. 7. LIME explanation for the misclassified statements by Facebook.

SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations): SHAP provided a complementary perspective by attributing token contributions to the prediction score based on Shapley values(refer to 8).

Fig. 8. SHAP explanation for the misclassified statements by Facebook.

Contrastive Explanations: This method focused on identifying features influencing classification towards one class rather than an alternative, valuable for nuanced Sinhala examples(refer to 9).

For the text "There are instances where racism has been used for political gain," correctly classified as not_hate_speech, the overall attribution score was negative (-4.30). The term "racism" exhibited a strong negative attribution (-3.0945), pushing towards hate_speech. Conversely, "political" showed a posi-

Word	Attribution Score
දේශපාලන	0.5532
වාසි	-0.2222
සඳහා	0.0576
ජාතිවාදය	-3.0945
යොදාගත්	-0.1364
අවිච්ඡිත	-0.1854
ආත්	-0.2231

True Label	Predicted Label	Attribution Label	Attribution Score
not_hate_speech	not_hate_speech (0.95)	Contrastive Explanation	-4.30

Legend: ■ Negative □ Neutral ■ Positive

Fig. 9. Contrastive explanation for a nuanced non-hate speech political commentary.

tive attribution (+0.5532), pushing towards not_hate_speech. This highlights a “tug-of-war” where contextual cues successfully override the strong signal from “racism,” leading to a correct, nuanced classification, demonstrating semantic mitigation and contextual understanding.

Comparing XAI methods, they often agreed on salient tokens but offered different perspectives (LIME for local importance, SHAP for baseline-relative contribution, contrastive for discriminative features). Collectively, they enhanced the transparency of the hate speech detection model, crucial for user trust and accountability under the Online Safety Act, enabling human review and contestation.

Qualitative Error Analysis A qualitative error analysis of the test set (3354 instances) revealed 259 misclassifications (7.72%), comprising 162 false positives (62.5%) and 97 false negatives (37.45%). False positives often stemmed from humorous or metaphorical expressions misinterpreted as hate speech—for example, the sarcastic Sinhala phrase “May the mosquitoes that come near your ear get cursed” triggered a misclassification due to the word “cursed.” Such errors raise concerns about over-censorship and the risk of unjustly flagging benign content, especially under the Online Safety Act. False negatives involved undetected hate speech with subtle cues like dehumanizing metaphors or sarcasm, such as calling someone a “cursed human animal.” These cases underline the challenges of capturing nuanced linguistic patterns and highlight the need for more targeted data collection, improved context modeling, and human oversight to ensure both accuracy and fairness in content moderation.

4.3 Interpretation of Results: Relevance to Sri Lanka’s Online Safety Act and the Human Factor

The framework effectively aligns with the goals of Sri Lanka’s Online Safety Act. Its strong hate speech detection performance shows that automated moderation is viable. The multi-agent fact verification system, using RAG and real-time search, provides a reliable method for addressing misinformation under

the Act. RAGAS evaluation confirms the accuracy and relevance of this hybrid approach. The integration of XAI meets the Act’s transparency and accountability requirements. By offering interpretable outputs, the system aids human moderators, supports legal reviews, and ensures fairness. Rather than replacing humans, the AI enhances their decision-making with justifications and evidence. This responsible, hybrid approach balances automation with human oversight, promoting effective and ethical Sinhala content moderation in line with the Act.

4.4 Comparison with Literature

Comparing findings highlights unique contributions in Sinhala and hybrid content moderation. Our hate speech detection performance (Accuracy: 0.9255, F1: 0.9222) is competitive with state-of-the-art Sinhala studies. The primary distinction is the novel hybrid framework architecture, integrating both hate speech detection and misinformation verification for comprehensive moderation. Explicit focus on explainability through LIME, SHAP, and Contrastive Explanations sets our hate speech detection component apart from studies prioritizing only predictive performance, vital for sensitive domains under legal frameworks like the Online Safety Act. The multi-agent misinformation verification system’s innovative use of a multi-agent architecture to orchestrate RAG and real-time web search for context-aware Sinhala verification is a significant contribution to misinformation detection in a low-resource language. Sinhala prompt engineering highlights successful adaptation challenges. Quantitative RAGAS evaluation supports RAG outputs and justifies the necessity of dynamic real-time search to complement static knowledge bases. This research pioneers an AI framework specifically designed to align with Sri Lanka’s Online Safety Act within a low-resource language context. Existing literature lacks comprehensive AI systems explicitly integrating legal accountability, transparency for legal review, and dynamic verification capabilities tailored to Sinhala’s linguistic and legal nuances. Our novel combination of individual techniques (transformers, RAG, multi-agent systems, XAI) within a hybrid framework constitutes a significant advancement addressing identified research gaps.

4.5 Implications of the Findings

The findings have significant theoretical and practical implications. The successful use of advanced AI techniques—including transformers, RAG, multi-agent systems, and explainability, in a low-resource language like Sinhala demonstrates their adaptability beyond high-resource settings and offers a valuable blueprint for AI system design in linguistically complex and sensitive domains. The integration of explainability and context-awareness within a unified framework highlights how trustworthy, multi-step reasoning systems can be built for tasks like fact verification. Practically, the framework supports human moderators by automating harmful content detection and providing clear, evidence-backed justifications, enhancing efficiency, transparency, and fairness. Its context-aware fact-checking mechanism promotes informed online discourse, while RAGAS

evaluations validate the system’s reliability. Most importantly, the framework directly aligns with the objectives of Sri Lanka’s Online Safety Act, offering a responsible, legally compliant solution for hate speech detection and misinformation verification tailored to local linguistic and societal needs.

4.6 Suggestions for Future Research

Building on the current findings and acknowledging existing limitations, future research should focus on both expanding the framework’s scope and deepening its societal relevance. One direction involves adapting the architecture to other critical decision-making domains where transparency and accountability are essential. Equally important is conducting in-depth studies on the legal and societal implications of deploying such AI systems in Sri Lanka to ensure responsible implementation. Technically, the framework could be enhanced by integrating multimodal capabilities, such as image and video analysis, to improve content understanding. Finally, broadening its linguistic reach to include other low-resource languages like Tamil, and addressing linguistic complexities such as Romanized Sinhala and code-mixing, would increase inclusivity and applicability across diverse user contexts.

5 CONCLUSION

This study addressed the need for transparent, context-aware Sinhala online content moderation within Sri Lanka’s Online Safety Act. We developed a hybrid AI framework integrating an explainable hate speech detection system and a multi-agent misinformation verification system. The hate speech module, leveraging a fine-tuned XLM-RoBERTa-base model with XAI techniques (LIME, SHAP, Contrastive Explanations), achieved high performance (see Results) and provided interpretable classifications. The misinformation system, built on a LangChain multi-agent architecture with RAG and real-time search, delivered reasoned Sinhala verification analyses, with RAGAS scores validating its effectiveness. Qualitative error analysis revealed limitations with nuanced language, underscoring the need for human oversight. This research demonstrates the feasibility of advanced AI for low-resource languages, aligning with the Act’s legal and ethical mandates through human-AI collaboration. Future work should enhance multilingual capabilities and explore real-world deployment. The framework offers a scalable solution for content moderation, with potential applications in other critical domains.

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